

MANAGEMENT TO IMPROVE STUDY PROGRAM PERFORMANCE AT PRIVATE UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract

Improving Study Program Performance is an important element in the process of quality assurance at private tertiary institutions. The quality assurance system needs to be implemented in a measurable and consistent manner to positively impact organizational governance within a university. This was then used as the background for conducting this research. The general purpose of this research is to analyze, describe, and get an overview of the Internal Quality Assurance System in an effort to improve the performance of study programs at private tertiary institutions, especially regarding input, process, and output. This research is based on theories: System, Quality Management which boils down to the theory of Quality Improvement from Juran (1989) and Permendikbud No. 3 of 2020 combined with Permenristekdikti No. 62 of 2016 by focusing on the stages of Determination, Implementation, Evaluation, Control, and Improvement (PPEPP). This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach to the case study method. The results of the study show that: (1) Input performance includes vision and mission, superior accreditation scores, recognition by external parties, education and teaching, research, and PKM at the two research locations that have been determined according to procedures and achieved the targets set. (2) The process through the determination, implementation, evaluation, control, and improvement of SPMI standards has been carried out properly and consistently and has been integrated with the latest technology. (3) Outcome performance related to improving the performance of the study programs has gone well, marked by the achievement of accreditation ratings and the results of the evaluation desk in the internal quality audit process with exceeding results. (4) There are still several obstacles in the SPMI development process related to improving the performance of study programs, namely limited quality of human resources, the readiness of technological devices, and resistance to changes in the SPMI process. Referring to the results of this study, it can be concluded that the implementation of the management of the internal quality assurance system has been running using the PPEPP cycle, indicating that the quality assurance system has been running as it should at the two research locations. Even in its implementation, it uses an application to implement quality assurance that is integrated and involves quality assurance institutions in each section (university, faculty, and study program level). The internal quality assurance system in the two research locations already refers to the main performance indicator targets. However, improving performance-oriented to specific performance indicators has not been maximized. Therefore the researcher proposes an SPMI model at the study program level which is equipped with Specific Performance Indicators as a research novelty.

Keywords: Determination, Implementation, Evaluation, Control, and Improvement of the Internal Quality Assurance System, and Study Program Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The quality assurance system is an effort made by universities to ensure that quality is maintained within an institution. Quality management is an effort and approach carried out by an organization that focuses on continuous improvement by maximizing the organization's competitiveness to realize the commitment, policies and quality targets that have been set. Quality management is a system that helps an organization, institution, company, or business entity to supervise every activity as well as the duties and responsibilities required to maintain the quality or qualities produced from planning, process to results.

Management of improving the quality of an institution or study program is a quality improvement approach that focuses on that entity, involving various methods based on available quantitative and qualitative data information. All institutional members are involved in ongoing efforts to increase the capacity and ability of the organization or institution to meet the needs of users and society. In the context of quality management development (MPM), there are various aspects that involve monitoring processes in institutions, both in curricular and administrative aspects. This process includes diagnosis and relies on the participation of all relevant parties.

In an effort to improve service quality, internal and external quality assurance institutions are needed. The Internal Quality Assurance System (SPMI) and External Quality Assurance System (SPME) in Higher Education certainly cannot be implemented easily, but many obstacles and constraints are also encountered by Higher Education Institutions, therefore it requires full commitment from all elements of higher education to implement SPMI successfully. Principles of autonomy, standardization, accuracy, planning and sustainability

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The method used in this research is a descriptive exploratory method with a qualitative case study type approach. In the qualitative approach, data analysis is conveyed verbally, to obtain comprehensive and in-depth information. The qualitative research method that the researcher used in this research is because the problem being studied is complex, dynamic, and full of meaning, so it is impossible for data on social situations that are complex, dynamic and whose problems are unclear to be captured using quantitative research methods. Apart from that, the use of this qualitative method is intended to understand in depth the application of SPMI in an effort to improve the performance of private universities.

The qualitative approach prioritizes the process rather than the results, checking the validity of the data and the research results are agreed upon by both parties, namely the researcher and the research subjects. In this research, what is explained about SPMI cycle management in an effort to improve the performance of private universities at Unpas and UBP Karawang is in accordance with findings in the field and compared with standard/tested theories and basic concepts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the discussion of this research, the results of the findings are explained and the internal quality assurance system management is described to improve the performance of the study program. The quality assurance system in higher education is an effort made by universities to continuously strive to improve the quality assurance system which has an impact on improving higher education performance. Next, the results of this research are analyzed and connected to theory and policy. According to Joseph Juran, quality is the suitability of product use (fitness for use) to meet customer needs and satisfaction. The suitability of the product user is based on five main characteristics, namely (1) technology; namely strength; (2) psychological, namely feeling or status; (3) time, namely reliability; (4) contractual, namely there is a guarantee; (5) ethics, namely good manners. According to Philip B Crosby, quality is conformance to requirements, namely in accordance with what is required or standardized. A product has quality if it complies with predetermined quality standards or criteria, these quality standards include raw materials, production processes and finished products.

Referring to Minister of Education and Culture Regulation no. 3 of 2020 concerning SN Dikti, Part Five, Article 22, Article 49 and Article 60 determine the minimum criteria for activities regarding SN Dikti. The SN Dikti assessment process and results carried out in an integrated manner must fulfill several elements including: a) Educational, which is an assessment to motivate implementation in order to continue to improve the quality of PPKM; b) Objective, which is an assessment based on assessment criteria and free from the influence of subjectivity; c) Accountable, which is an assessment carried out with clear criteria and procedures that are understood by researchers and PkM implementers; d) Transparent, which is an assessment whose procedures and assessment results can be accessed by all stakeholders and to prepare students for the world of work from the start. Furthermore, the Internal Quality Assurance System according to Permenristekdikti No. 62 of 2016 is a quality assurance activity carried out by each PT autonomously or independently to control and improve the implementation of Higher Education in a planned and sustainable manner with the PPEPP cycle. Furthermore, in this research, the relationship between internal quality assurance to improve performance is connected to performance theory

According to Dale Timpe, performance is a person's level of achievement in an organization or company that can increase productivity (Dale, 2012) . Apart from achievement, performance is also influenced by motivation, as stated by Timpe, to build worker productivity and motivation, there are two things that must be done: first, look for payment for one's individual work; and second, help them achieve payment for each additional task assigned so that both agency and individual needs are met (Dale, 1999) .

Based on the understanding above, quality improvement management has the following principles: 1) quality improvement must be implemented in the Institution, 2). Quality improvement can only be implemented with good leadership; 3). Quality improvement must be based on data and facts, both qualitative and quantitative; 4). Quality improvement must empower and involve all existing elements ; 5). Quality improvement

aims to ensure that institutions/schools can provide satisfaction to students, parents and the community.

Apart from the theoretical explanation above, regulations are needed that can support the implementation of the Quality Assurance System. According to Article 53 and Article 52 paragraph (4) of the Higher Education Law as also regulated in Permenristekdikti No. 62 of 2016 concerning SPM Dikti, SPM Dikti consists of. An important basic matter is that PTs are obliged to submit data and information on PT operations to be stored in PD Dikti, and guarantee their truth and accuracy. Apart from that, it is also regulated in Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 3 of 2020, namely that National Higher Education Standards are a standard unit which includes National Education Standards, plus Research Standards and Community Service Standards. National Higher Education Standards aim to: a. guarantee the achievement of the goals of Higher Education which play a strategic role in educating the nation's life, advancing science and technology by applying humanities values as well as the sustainable acculturation and empowerment of the Indonesian nation; b. guarantee that learning in study, research and community service programs organized by universities in all jurisdictions of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia achieves quality in accordance with the criteria set out in the National Higher Education Standards; and c. encourage higher education institutions in all jurisdictions of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia to achieve quality learning, research and community service that exceeds the criteria set out in the National Higher Education Standards on an ongoing basis. From this, this discussion will link the research objectives with the conceptual basis and connect with the results of the research carried out, then connect with the stages of the quality assurance system in determining, implementing, evaluating, controlling, improving as well as explaining the problems and solutions obtained from research result.

Implementation of SPMI in 2 Research Locations

SPMI implementation	FKIP Unpas	UBP Karawang
SPMI is application based	SITI SAPTO	WordPress
SPMI Institute	BPMI-GKM-UPM	LPM-GKM-GJM
SPMI Application Module	QN-QL	LPM-AMI system

After carrying out research at two research locations, several stages of implementing the internal quality assurance system can be described as follows:

1) Determination

From the research results at the Determination stage at Pasundan University and Buana Perjuangan Karawang University, standard setting activities refer to policies consisting of SN Dikti and Dikti Standards set by universities. At the standard setting stage, BPMI Unpas and LPM UBP Karawang along with the unit responsible for the relevant standards formulated a standard statement and indicators of its achievement. The standards implemented are formulated by referring to Republic of Indonesia Law No. 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education, Minister of Education and Culture Regulation No. 3 of 2020 concerning National Standards for Higher Education, the Statutes of Pasundan University

and UBP Karawang, the Strategic Plan (Renstra) of Pasundan University and UBP Karawang, and the Vision and the Mission of the University. These standard formulations are outlined in the SPMI Document which consists of the Quality Policy Document, Quality Standard Document, Quality Manual Document, and Quality Form Document

Tabel 1: Format Tabel

Kepala Tabel	Kepala Kolom Tabel	
	Sub-kepala Kolom	Sub-kepala Kolom
Isi	Isi tabel	Isi tabel

2) Implementation

After carrying out the determination stages, entry into the second cycle, Implementation (P) of Higher Education Standards, is the activity of fulfilling standards consisting of SN Dikti and Higher Education Standards set by universities. The essence of the standard implementation stage at Pasundan University is that Pasundan University carries out all applicable standards. The standards (and other SPMI documents) that have been formulated by BPMI and determined by the Chancellor for implementation, are socialized to all work units within Pasundan University, to then be used as a reference in implementing performance activities.

Referring to the description above, the implementation of quality assurance in the two research locations also has an impact on improving employee performance in relation to better study program performance. This is proven by the AMI results which show the study program consistently implements the set standards. This is in accordance with expert opinion which reveals that there are two factors that influence employee performance, namely: a. Internal factors, namely factors related to a person's characteristics, include attitudes, personality traits, physical characteristics, desires or motivation, age, gender, education, work experience, cultural background and other personal variables. b. External factors are factors that influence employee performance that come from the environment, including organizational policies, leadership, actions of co-workers such as training and supervision, wage systems and the social environment (Dale, 1999) .

3) Evaluation

In the third cycle stage, Evaluation (E) of the implementation of Higher Education Standards, namely comparison activities between the output of standard fulfillment activities with standards consisting of SN Dikti and Higher Education Standards that have been set by higher education institutions. Evaluation is proven by the following activities:

1) External Evaluation (Accreditation)

Quality improvement is essentially focused on continuous improvement. In fact, strategies for improving the quality of education in higher education must be in accordance with the relevance of education which includes several aspects such as curriculum, providers, educational experts, educational facilities, and leadership of educational units. This is in

line with the opinion which reveals that various strategies are needed for all study programs to achieve Superior accreditation as an effort to shape and develop all the potential that exists in institutions and students in order to prepare those who have professional academic abilities, who can apply and develop at the undergraduate level. (Sulistiyoko & Hafidzi, 2021) .

2) Internal Quality Audit (AMI)

Internal Quality Audit is a systematic, independent and documented testing process to ensure that the implementation of activities at a PT is in accordance with procedures and the results are in accordance with standards to achieve institutional goals. Internal Quality Audit: Audit carried out to determine the level of conformity of the implementation of activities to the organization's own internal standards (Internal quality standards*), Regulations, Procedures, Work Instructions, in the context of improving institutional quality and reducing the risk of standards not being achieved/decreasing quality.

According to Amin (2012: 136) internal audit is an objective independent assurance and consulting activity designed to add value and improve organizational operations, helping organizations and disciplines to evaluate and improve the effectiveness of risk management, control and governance processes. According to Sukrisno Agoes (2013:204) internal audit is an examination carried out by the company's internal audit department of the company's financial reports and accounting records as well as compliance with predetermined top management policies and compliance with government regulations and the provisions of applicable professional associations (Mufriha & Suparman, 2022) .

Internal quality audit (AMI) is a key factor in the management of an organization to be able to provide useful data for the purposes of evaluating and improving/increasing the effectiveness of the system it has, and is a fundamental technique whose results are used as input for management review activities as required by management system standards. AMI as an implementation of the evaluation of the PPEPP cycle, carries out a systematic, independent and documented testing process to ensure that the implementation of activities in higher education is in accordance with procedures and the results are in accordance with policies/standards/guidelines/provisions/regulations to achieve institutional goals. In its implementation, AMI is not just an assessment/assessment, but rather matching the suitability between implementation and planning of an activity/program. In other words, AMI checks the conformity between the quality standards set out in the Quality Management system and their implementation by work units at Pasundan University.

4) Control

After carrying out the next evaluation at the fourth cycle stage, Control (P) of the implementation of Higher Education Standards, namely the activity of analyzing the causes of standards consisting of SN Dikti and Higher Education Standards that have been set by higher education institutions which are not achieved for correction. Control is proven by the following activities:

1) Management Review Meeting (RTM)

RTM is a meeting held by management periodically to review the performance of the quality management system and institutional service performance to ensure the continuity, suitability, adequacy and effectiveness of the quality management system and service management. The Management Review Meeting (RTM) is the highest meeting in the implementation of Internal Quality Assurance System (SPMI) activities which are carried out within a certain period of time. RTM aims to evaluate system performance as a whole at the Study Program Management Unit (UPPS) and University levels. The discussions in the RTM and RTL answer the issues faced by the Study Program (Prodi) and are proven by the findings from AMI and the results of survey analysis or feedback from all stakeholders regarding the implementation of activities at both the Study Program and UPPS levels. Unpas and UBP Karawang implemented RTM in order to evaluate and control the results of internal audits so that they become material for subsequent improvements. This is in line with the opinion which reveals that in principle quality assurance must be carried out seriously. Support from various parties is something that will really help educational institutions in its implementation. Internal quality assurance must be carried out periodically and continuously to achieve a culture of quality in educational institutions (Fadhli, 2020) .

5) Enhancement

In the final stage or fifth cycle, Improvement (P) of Higher Education Standards, namely activities to improve standards consisting of SN Dikti and Standards of Higher Education so that they are higher than the standards consisting of SN Dikti and Standards of Higher Education that have been determined. Improving the Higher Education Standards at Pasundan University begins with analyzing the results of the RTM, especially the results of discussions on the agenda regarding Main Strategic Issues, and management action plans *for overcoming problems*, as well as new ideas for continuous progress (*continuous quality improvement*) at the University. Next, a SWOT analysis and risk-based management mapping is carried out *by placing action plans and possibilities*, as well as appointing the person responsible for implementing them. At the specified target time, the program implementation results are checked and re-evaluated. Implementation is proven by the following activities and documents. Accreditation is a form of external quality assurance system (SPME). Accreditation is an assessment activity to determine the suitability of study programs and universities. Study program accreditation is an assessment activity to determine the suitability of a study program, while tertiary accreditation is an assessment activity to determine the suitability of a college. Accreditation is carried out through an assessment of the outcomes of implementing SPMI by higher education institutions to determine accredited status and accredited ranking of study programs and/or tertiary institutions.

CONCLUSION

1. General Conclusion

Based on the results of research related to the implementation of internal quality assurance system management that has been running using the PPEPP cycle, it shows that in the two research locations the quality assurance system has been running as it should, even in its implementation using applications for integrated quality assurance implementation and involving quality assurance institutions in each section. (University level, faculty and study program). The internal quality assurance system at the two research locations refers to key performance indicator targets. However, performance improvement oriented towards specific performance indicators has not been optimal

2. Special Conclusion

- a. Quality assurance activities at the two research locations have been carried out well and systematically. This is characterized by the process of determining standard indicators which go through stages that are adjusted to the provisions of applicable regulations. Standard setting activities refer to policies consisting of SN Dikti and Dikti Standards set by universities. Determination is proven by SPMI documents as the basis for Quality Assurance starting from SPMI Policy, SPMI Manual, SPMI Standards and SPMI Forms or supporting formats
- b. Implementation of quality assurance activities at the two research locations has been carried out effectively and efficiently. This is characterized by the fulfillment of standards consisting of SN Dikti and Dikti Standards set by universities. Implementation is proven by documents such as decision letters related to the Internal Quality Assurance Institution and the internal audit team
- c. Quality assurance evaluation activities at the two research locations have been carried out well according to the specified periodization. This is characterized by comparison activities between the output of standard fulfillment activities and standards consisting of SN Dikti and Dikti Standards that have been set by universities. Evaluation is proven by activities such as: External Evaluation (Accreditation), Internal Quality Audit (AMI), Internal Quality Audit Study Program (AMI), Teaching and Learning Process Evaluation Work Unit (PBM), Stakeholder Satisfaction Survey Quality Assurance Institute Report (LPM), Faculty Quality Control Group Report (GKM) Study Program
- d. Quality assurance control activities at the two research locations were carried out systematically through analysis of the causes of standards consisting of SN Dikti and Dikti Standards set by higher education institutions which were not achieved for correction. Control is proven by the following activities. Management Review Meeting (RTM), AMI Follow-up Form, Follow-up Results
- e. Activities to improve quality assurance at the two research locations were carried out in good stages through standard improvement activities consisting of SN Dikti and Standards Dikti so that they were higher than the standards consisting of SN Dikti and Standards Dikti that had been determined, and referring to the Main Performance

Indicators (IKU) and Additional Performance Indicators (IKT) but there are no specific performance indicators (IKK).

f. Problem

The research results reveal that in implementing the quality assurance system in relation to improving study program performance there are still several obstacles faced, including the quantity and quality of human resources owned, financing for system development, technological readiness and some resistance to system implementation.

g. Solution

Referring to the problems that became research findings, researchers see the need for concrete and concrete solutions to overcome this, namely by carrying out HR competency development, analyzing the need for technological readiness equipment and providing outreach to stakeholders so as to minimize resistance to system implementation.

Bibliography

- 1) Dale Timpe. (2023). *PERFORMANCE Human Resources Management Series* . Gramedia Asri Media.
- 2) Alfian Tri Kuntoro. (2019). Islamic Education Quality Management. *Journal of Education* , 7 (1), 84–97.
- 3) Baltaru, R.D. (2019). Do non-academic professionals enhance universities' performance? Reputation vs. organisation. *Studies in Higher Education*, 44 (7), 1183–1196. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2017.1421156>
- 4) BPMI Unpas. (2023). *BPMI-BPI Internal Quality Assurance Profile, Pasundan University* .
- 5) Cartin, T. (1999). *Principles and Practices of Organizational Performance Excellence* . ASQ Quality Press.
- 6) Dale, T. (1999). *Human Resource Management Series: Performance* . Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 7) Dale, T. (2012). *Science and Art of Business Management (Leading People) Series* . PT. Elex Media Komputindo.
- 8) Dhal, P. K. (2021). Quality Management in Education. *SSRN Electronic Journal, January*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3726921>
- 9) Edward, S. (2006). *Total Quality Management in Education* . IRCiSoD.
- 10) EKO Supriyanto. (2008). *Quality Assurance Model Of Muhammadiyah Higher Education* . Semarang State University.
- 11) Ericksen, J., & Dyer, L. (2005). Toward a strategic human resource management model of high reliability organizational performance. *International Journal of Human Resource Management* , 16 (6), 907–928. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09585190500120731>
- 12) Fadhli, M. (2020). Internal and External Quality Assurance Systems in Higher Education Institutions. *AL-TANZIM: Journal of Islamic Education Management* , 4 (2), 53–65. <https://doi.org/10.33650/al-tanzim.v4i2.1148>
- 13) Fathul Jannah. (2014). *Academic Quality Management Of Islamic Religious Universities (Case Study Of Stain And Stis In Samarinda)* . Uin Alauddin Makassar.

- 14) Ferils, M., & Syarifuddin. (2020). Implementation of an internal quality assurance system at the Muhammadiyah Mamuju College of Economics. *Competitiveness* , 9 (1), 21–36.
- 15) Fitriani, LPW, & Kemenuh, IAA (2021). Improving The Quality Assurance System In Higher Education Through The Implementation Of Integrated Quality Management In Education. *Door: Quality Assurance Center* , 2 (2).
- 16) Garvin, D. A. (1987). *Managing Quality* . The Free Press.
- 17) Gaspersz. (2002). *Total Quality Management* . Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 18) Gibson, James I, Jhon M. Ivancevich, and James H Donnelly, J. (1994). *Organizations: Behavior, Structure, and processes. Translation* . Erlangga.
- 19) Goetsch, D. L. & Davis, S. (1995). *Introduction to Total Quality, Quality, Productivity, Competitiveness*. Prentice Hall International Inc.
- 20) Handayani, N. Nyoman L., & Ni Ketut Erna Muliastri. (2021). Determination of the Internal Quality Assurance System on Improving the Quality of Higher Education. 2(2). *Journal of Quality Assurance Center* , 2 (2), 2746–7074.
- 21) Hannushek. (2008). *Education production function. The New Palgrave Dictionary of Economics, Second Edition* . Palgrave Encyclopedia.
- 22) Hasbullah. (2021). Implementation of Integrated Quality in Higher Education. *Tarbiyah Islamiyah: Scientific Journal of Islamic Religious Education*, 11 (1), 69–77.
<https://doi.org/10.18592/jtipai.v11i1.4852>
- 23) Juran, M. (1989). *Juran on Leadership for Quality: An Executive Handbook* . Free Press.
- 24) Ministry of Education and Culture. (2020). *Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2020 concerning National Higher Education Standards* .
- 25) Ministry of Education and Culture. (2016). *Permenristekdikti number 62 of 2016* .
- 26) LLDIKTI IV. (nd). *PPID LLDIKTI IV* . <https://ppid.lldikti4.or.id/>